

INVESTIGATION OF LOW-VELOCITY IMPACT AND CAI BEHAVIOR OF HYBRID SANDWICH COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

A structure's ability to withstand post impact loading is heavily reliant on a critical assessment of its mechanical properties. Three different sandwich structures made from carbon epoxy skins, foam-core and glass fiber were manufactured by vacuum-assisted resin injection (VARI) process and subjected to low velocity impacts. The damaged panels were then tested for their compression-after-impact (CAI) strength. Internal and external damage that resulted from these impact events was carefully evaluated. Impact damage mode consisted of matrix cracking, fiber breaking, foam cracking and debonding.

Laminates with pure glass facesheet was found to be a very robust energy absorber and thus had a good impact resistance properties compared to laminates of pure carbon fiber which had the worse impact resistance among the sandwich structures. Hybrid panel with ply mode of [C2/G2/Foamcore/G2/C2] could provide higher maximum contact force and absorb more impact energy with carbon fiber breaking on the contact surface.

In CAI test, wrinkling of facesheet and buckling of foam and skin are the two main damage modes. [C4/Foam core/C4] shows highest compress strength decline rate, while [G4/Foam core/G4] shows lowest rate. Decline rate of [C2/G2/Foam core/G2/C2] is very low but the compress strength of its undamaged specimen is not high. Although not visually apparent, the facesheet delamination damage was found to be quite detrimental to the load bearing capacity of the sandwich panel, underscoring the need for reliable damage detection techniques for composite sandwich structures.

1 INTRODUCTION

The use of composite materials in structural applications ranging from aircraft and space structures to automotive and biomedical applications has experience a growing interest worldwide. However activities during manufacturing, maintenance and other normal operations are prone to impact since tools might fall and so are other impact related activities causing major concern in composite applications in structures. Hybrid structures enable the combination of the best material properties of different material groups in one structure and thus offer interesting possibilities for new applications. For example in bending test, two thin but stiff and strong facesheets sustain in-plane loads, while the thick, light-weight and weaker core sustains the shear load. However, under impact load, the integrity and damage tolerance of sandwich panels are usually very low Evci et al.[1] have studied the impact response of composite materials and found that material behavior and low velocity impact performance of fiber reinforced composites depend on several factors such as material properties of reinforcement, fabric structure, mechanical properties of matrix, number and order of layers in

composite structure and projectile velocity. Damage initiation and growth are closely dependent on both impact source properties (e.g. impact force, impact velocity, impact energy) and impact response of the material (e.g. material strength, displacement under force, energy dissipation, impact duration)[2-4]. Some experimental investigations have been carried out by Hosur et al.[5] to determine the response of four different combinations of hybrid laminates subjected to low velocity impact loading. They have indicated that there was considerable improvement in the load carrying capability of hybrid composites as compared to carbon/epoxy laminates with slight reduction in stiffness. Kim and Kang[6] carried out studies on plain weave glass/epoxy laminates. They observed that, as the thickness increases, absorbed impact energy by deflection decreases whereas that by local indentation increases.

Residual strength of impact damaged specimens can be measured in response to tensile, compressive and shear loading conditions. In addition, fatigue loading is often of interest and examples of results are available in research by Tomblin et al.[7] and Shyprykevich et al.[8]. However, the out of plane displacement of sandwich panel components associated with impact damage as shown in various impact tests, result in significant stress raising and instabilities during compressive loading making compression after impact (CAI) the primary tool of residual strength determination. Tomblin et al [9] showed that CAI residual strength is higher for a similar size damage location in sandwich panels since impact damage does not extend through the entire core and does not affect the un-impacted facesheet for low velocity impacts. However, the CAI strength of a composite laminate found in material property data sheets is usually worse than the open hole compressive specimen with the hole of an equal size. The creation of CAI strength values through statistical analysis will be further explained in references to the work by Nettles and Jackson [10].

The aim of this project is to develop a reliable, faithful and fully validated experiment for low velocity impact and compression after impact behavior of sandwich panels consisting of woven carbon/epoxy facesheets, glass fiber and a PVC foam core. Three sandwich panels with dimension of 100mm×100 mm×16 mm with ply of [C4/Foam core/C4],[G2/C2/Foam core/C2/G2],and [G4/Foam core/G4] are manufactured and impacted with energy level of 30 J. Peak load, contact time, and absorbed energy were analyzed after impact. The damage modes of different specimens are then studied by visual inspection. Moreover, compression after impact (CAI) test is carried out to understand the residual strength of different sandwich panels after impact, and failure modes formed in the compression test were also analyzed. This work fits into the wider area of damage and residual strength modelling for composite structures, which is a very active field of research.

2 EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

2.1 Materials and specimen preparation

The host material during the VARI process was Derakane411-350 epoxy vinyl ester resin, which could be cured at ambient temperature. Epoxy matrix is Bisphenol A, Styrene (phenylethylene) content is 45 wt%, viscosity at 25 °C is 350 cps, USA, DERAKANE.

The hardening agent is Methyl Ethyl Ketone Peroxide (MEKP), and the accelerating agent is Dimethylaniline. At a mass ratio of 1:1%:0.1% resin is mixed with the accelerating and hardening agent with the reinforced material being plain weave glass fabric cloth and carbon fabric cloth. Fig 1 shows the two-dimensional orthogonal plain woven fabric cloth used in the experiment. The parameters of the different materials used in the experiment are given in Table 1 where g_w , g_f are the gap between adjacent strands and a_w , a_f are the strand width. The surface density of foam core is 900 g/m² and the thickness is 12 mm while the superscript w and f indicates the warp and fill direction of the woven fabric respectively. Foam core with special surface treatment is selected so as to ensure the fluidity of the resin as shown in Fig 2. The surface treatment of the foam had a dimension of 2mm diameter of through-thickness diversion outlet, distance between diversion trenches is 20 mm, and the width and depth of diversion trenches is 2mm.

Material	a_w (mm)	g_w (mm)	a_f (mm)	g_f (mm)	Surface density(g/m^2)
Carbon fabric	3.0	0.19	2.9	0.6	300
Glass fabric	5.0	1.0	4.1	1.2	500

Table 1: Dimension of plain woven fabric clothes.

Sample	pure composites		carbon		hybrid composites		pure glass composites	
	C1	C1-1	C2	C2-1	C3	C3-1		
Thickness	4.5	16.5	3.7	15.7	4.8	14.8		

Table 2: The thickness of different specimens.

Fig.1: Material composition and dimensions of sandwich composites.

Specimen manufacturing was done by adopting the vacuum-assisted resin injection (VARI) process. This was done by manufacturing three different kinds of laminated facesheets and another three foam-filled sandwich panels for the experiment. The ply modes of the laminated facesheets are $[G_4]$, $[G_2/C_2]$, $[C_4]$, and are denoted hereafter as C1, C2, C3. The ply modes of the panels are $[G_4/\text{Foam core}/G_4]$, $[G_2/C_2/\text{Foam core}/C_2/G_2]$, $[C_4/\text{Foam core}/C_4]$, as demonstrated in Fig 2. After an accurate dimensions of the various specimen was achieved and properly arranged ready to be prepared, a glass square plate was placed at the bottom as holder, and then release agent was evenly coated on mold surface. Peel ply and silk ply were then used to cover the foam and different woven fabric placed on the glass holder. The mold was closed by vacuum bag and sealant. The low viscosity resin was infused by vacuum to impregnate foam core as seen in Fig 3, and then the system was cured at room temperature. Note that the pressure of vacuum bag should be controlled at vacuum level of 600 mbar to prevent the foam core from collapsing. To test the mechanical behaviors of foam core sandwich panels with different facesheets, dimensions of specimens used in mechanical test were tailored to be $100 \times 100 \text{mm}^2$, the thickness of different specimens are shown in Table 2.

Fig 2: Different foam core sandwich assisted structures and codes.

Fig3: Specimen preparation using vacuum resin injection process

3 LOW-VELOCITY IMPACT TEST

Initial impact tests with 30J energies were conducted to produce impact damage for subsequent loading. The purpose of these initial tests is to find the existence of the threshold energy that causes impact damage which can be visually detected for this class of sandwich composites. A total of 6 specimens were impacted in this research work and impact fixture was utilized to provide the necessary support for the specimens during impact. Three different laminates and three different foam-core sandwich structures were tested under low velocity impact. Low-velocity impact testing was performed through the use of the Instron Dynatup 9250HV Drop Weight Impact Testing Machine .The test machine is made by the standard of ASTM D5628-07, as shown in Fig 4 Specimens of dimension 100×100mm² were positioned along all edges of the fixture leaving unexposed circular opening for impact. By controlling the impact energy around 30J, all tests were carried out through the use of a 12mm steel hemispherical impactor which weighed about 15kg. The test matrix obtained by using this impact testing machine is tabulated in table 4

Type of test	Composite structure	Number of samples tested	Impact energy(J)	Sample dimension(mm)
Impact test	Composite laminate	3	30J	100×100
Impact test	Composite sandwich structure	3	30J	100×100

Table 3: Impact test matrix

Fig 4: Equipment used in the impact test

4 COMPRESSION AFTER IMPACT TEST

In order to analyze how impact damage affects the strength of a structure, compression after impact test (CAI) is carried out to access the residual strength. Experimental approach in obtaining the residual compressive strength of composite sandwich panels subjected to low-velocity impact test could be attributed to the results obtained in CAI tests. The instrument of choice used in compression tests of initial and impacted sandwich panels with different types of facesheets was the Instron universal testing machine (Zwick/Roell), while compression test specimen used came in size 40 mm × 80 mm with varying thickness depending on the facesheet and core combinations as depicted in Table 2. A specimen is selected and carefully fixed at one end in longitudinal direction and compressed on the other end under displacement control until the ultimate catastrophic failure appears. Three specimens are tested to evaluate their average mechanical properties with displacement rate of 2 mm/min. Three unimpacted specimens of each experiment are also tested to be used as the controlled group.

During the CAI test the force-displacement history was obtained through the use of a data acquisition system whereas specimen damage behavior is seen through visual observation. In order to obtain the Compression after impact (CAI) strength of specimen, Dividing the maximum load by the cross sectional area then serves as the formula for finding the residual strength of sandwich structures as shown below

$$\sigma_c = \frac{F_{\max}}{w \cdot t} \quad (1)$$

Where σ_c is the ultimate compressive residual strength (Mpa), F_{\max} is the maximum force prior to failure (N), w and t are the width and thickness of specimen, respectively.

Fig 5: Measurement used in compression after impact test.

5 RESULT AND DISCUSSION

5.1 Failure modes of laminates and sandwich panels after low-velocity impact test

Fig 6 and Fig 7 show the damage modes of composite laminates and foam-filled sandwich panels. A close look at the different damages inflicted by the low-velocity impact test for different types of composite laminates and foam-filled sandwich panels shows some differences.

Composite laminates, pure glass fiber, hybrid, and pure carbon fiber composite laminates were all completely penetrated and round holes were formed at the contact regions.

Contrary to composite laminates the foam-filled sandwich structures had a variety of damages found at the contact surfaces, but the presence of foam in the structure enabled them to maintain a perfect condition at the bottom surfaces. However, debonding between pure carbon fiber facesheet and foam core was observed in the panels with pure carbon facesheet. Pure glass fiber and hybrid facesheet showed a particularly rhombus-like shape around the impact damage regions and also an extension of this shape along the warp and fill direction of this woven fabric. On the other hand sandwich panels composed of pure carbon fiber and foam-core had a round crater made at its contact region as the

impactor penetrated the carbon fiber facesheet. [G₄/Foam core/G₄] panel only have delamination failures, while in panel with layer form [C₄/Foam core/C₄], delamination together with local fiber breaking were noticed. It is worthy to note that for the hybrid panel that is [G₂/C₂/Foam core/C₂/G₂], local fiber breaking was observed in damage region.

Fig 6: Failure mode of laminated panel after impact

Fig 7: Transverse fracture morphology and failure mode of foam core sandwich structure after impact. Note (I) delamination, (II) fiber breaking, (III) foam cracking

(a) Delamination area of laminate panels

(b) Delamination area of foam sandwich structure

Fig 8: Delamination area of different specimens

Damage mode is largely dependent on both fiber stacking sequence of facesheet and the interface characteristics of facesheet and foam-core. Under impact load it's observed that all composite laminates were completely penetrated during impact and also impact energy being absorbed by fiber breaking and delamination as seen in Fig 6. In designing foam-core sandwich panels, studies shows that one of the most important factors during this process is the perforation threshold. Due to that the impact energy we used in this paper does not exceed the perforation threshold of panel with layer form [G₄/Foam core/G₄], the main failure mode is delamination. The perforation threshold of [G₂/C₂/Foam core/C₂/G₂] may be around 30J, which would result in fiber breaking and delamination. However, for [C₄/Foam core/C₄] the impact energy was absorbed by fiber breaking and local delamination, shown in Fig 7. Different studies have proven that carbon fiber as compared to other types of fibers are much

more brittle. Likewise in this study we observe that the dominant damage mode after low-velocity impact on specimen with carbon fiber was fiber breaking.

5.2 Contact force and impact energy history of sandwich panels under low-velocity impact

The typical contact-time (F-t) curves of the prepared composite laminates and sandwich panels subjected to the impact energy of 30J are depicted In Fig3.5 and Fig3.6 respectively.

Fig 9: Contact force and impact energy history of different laminates.

Fig 10: Contact force and impact energy history of different foam-core sandwich panels

Fig 11: Peak force and displacement obtained by low-velocity test for different laminates and sandwich panels

Contact force, defined as the reaction force applied by specimen to the impactor, is an important parameter for charactering impact resistance of material. The use of a data acquisition system was the system of choice used in obtaining the variations of contact force as a function of contact time. Fig 9 shows that the F-t curves increased at first and then decreased meaning the samples C1, C2, and C3 were completely penetrated absorbing the partial impact energy through fiber breaking, matrix failure, and interlayer delamination. Pure glass fiber laminates however had the maximum contact force $5.27 \pm 0.03 \text{KN}$, while the pure carbon fiber laminates had the minimum contact force $1.01 \pm 0.04 \text{KN}$, as listed in Table 3.

Fig 10 shows a unique F-t curves as compared to the other types of panels. All the F-t curves are in mountain-like shapes while the F-t curves of $[G_2/C_2/\text{Foam core}/C_2/G_2]$, $[C_4/\text{Foam core}/C_4]$ on one hand had double force peaks. The first force peak was caused by the contact between the impactor and contact facesheet, and the second force peak was formed due to the contact between the impactor and inner foam core after contact facesheet was penetrated. The F-t curves of $[G_2/C_2/\text{Foam core}/C_2/G_2]$ and $[C_4/\text{Foam core}/C_4]$, are in mountain-like shapes with double force peaks. The Initial peak force was formed as a result of the contact between the impactor and contact surface while the second peak force occurred as a result of the contact between the impactor and inner foam core after a complete penetration of the contact facesheet. The second peak force for the specimen $[C_4/\text{Foam core}/C_4]$ is larger than the first peak force while the F-t curves of $[G_4/\text{Foam core}/G_4]$ on the other hand shows a single force peak, which corresponds to the results where fiber breaking did not happen in the facesheet of sandwich panels and the impact load can be supported by the elastic deformation. Table 4 lists the peak force, deformation, energy, and the slow down rate of velocity at the peak force of different laminates and panels. Pure glass fiber laminates had the maximum deformation with the

value of 7.63 ± 0.11 mm. The comparison of the peak force and displacement of all the specimen shown in the bar chart thus Fig 11 gives a clearer and in-depth understanding of the this result.

Samples	Time	First peak force(KN)	Deformation(mm)	Energy(J)	Velocity slow down(%)
C1	3.25 ± 0.008	5.27 ± 0.03	7.63 ± 0.11	18.78 ± 1.05	51.82 ± 5.47
C2	2.76 ± 0.08	4.30 ± 0.24	6.65 ± 0.13	12.56 ± 1.62	27.07 ± 4.98
C3	0.91 ± 0.06	1.01 ± 0.04	2.34 ± 0.15	1.52 ± 0.11	1.03 ± 0.15
C1-1	2.82349 ± 0.07	5.96 ± 0.05	6.19 ± 0.08	20.84 ± 0.92	42.29 ± 2.6
C1-2	3.52478 ± 0.12	6.84 ± 0.59	6.79 ± 0.08	27.40 ± 1.16	65.85 ± 5.40

Table 4: Parameters at peak contact force obtained by the low-velocity impact test

5.3 Contact force and displacement of different foam-core sandwich panels in low-velocity impact

Fig 12 shows the contact force-displacement (F-d) curves of sandwich panels subjected to the impact energy of 30J. Two kinds of shapes can be seen from the F-d curve thus closed and unclosed curves. The closed curves signifies that only indentation was left on the corresponding specimen when it is subjected to impact load, but it was not suffered severe damage. Furthermore, the curves in Fig11a are closed, and the curves in Fig11b and Fig11c are unclosed.

Fig 12: Variations of contact force as a function of displacement for different sandwich panels during the low-velocity impact test.

Fig 13: Variation of velocity with deflection for different sandwich panels under impact energy

The velocity of impact head as a function of deflection of all sandwich panels under the impact energy of 30J is shown in Fig 13. From the figure we notice that the velocity of impact head reached the maximum value when impact head contacts the surface of specimens, and then decreased to zero with different velocity rates. The negative value that was recorded by the velocity indicates the rebounding of the impactor.

5.4 Compression after impact result of sandwich panels

Compressive properties of the impacted specimens are lower than that of the non-impacted specimen. A critical look at Fig14 shows that with increasing strain all the compressive stress curves appeared as a linear form. The curve then recorded a sharp decline at certain a strain value but still continuously records stress resistance as samples continue to deform. This is evident in the small bump recorded throughout the various stress-strain curves provided in this dissertation

Fig 14: Typical stress-strain curves of different sandwich panels before and after impact.

5.5 compressive strength and strength decline ratio of impacted and non-impacted specimen

Fig 15 shows the comparison results of compressive strength and strength decline ratio of impacted and initial panels. The strength decline ratio can be obtained from the formula $(S_i - S_r)/S_r \times 100\%$ where S_i is the initial compressive strength and S_r is the residual strength of the specimens. Owing to the fact that bending stiffness of undamaged panel is comparatively higher than that of the damaged panel due to the low-velocity impact on specimen, residual strength of damaged structure is likewise lower than that of its undamaged structure. It is clear from the strength decline ratio results that the compressive strength of panels with layer form [C₄/Foam core/C₄], declines from 11.42±0.44MPa to 2.7±1.56MPa, the corresponding strength decline ratio is calculated to be 76.37±11.18%, which tends to be the largest value of all the panel specimens. By contrast, the compressive strength of panels is significantly reduced after subjected to impact load. In detail, the impacted panels with layer form [G₂/C₂/Foam core/C₂/G₂] has the compressive strength of 7.58±0.86MPa, while [G₄/Foam core/G₄] has the compressive strength of 39.09±6.13MPa which is the lowest value among all panels.

Fig 15: Compressive strength of impacted and non-impacted sandwich panels

5.6 Failure mode of impacted and non-impacted specimen

Fig 16 shows the failure modes of the initial and impacted specimens after compression tests. One can see that the major differences of failure modes for the initial and impacted specimens are their buckling location. Generally, the buckling of initial specimens is located at the end of the specimens as seen in Fig 16a, while the buckling of impacted specimens is taken place at the damage region. The main reason is that the damage region is becoming unstable and the indentation is propagating with the increasing compressive load, which would cause a reduction of the load carrying capacity of panels, as shown in Fig 16b.

Fig 16: Damage modes of un-impacted and impacted specimens after compression test.

The common failure modes of specimen C1-1 are facesheet micro-buckling and wrinkling, foam core cracking, and debonding. However for specimen C2-1 we notice that debonding occurs at the interface between foam and facesheet. The compressive failure modes of the initial specimen C3-1 are fiber debonding and foam buckling, while specimens C1-1, and C2-1 shares a common failure mode which is the buckling failure located around the indentation regions. Fiber breaking is observed at the end of specimen C1-1. Within the interface of glass fiber and carbon fiber facesheets, debonding of fiber was seen in specimen C2-2. The main failure modes of specimen C3-1 are the debonding of pure carbon fiber facesheets, shear damage, and foam core cracking.

9 CONCLUSIONS

This experimental study deals with the investigation of impact response and residual compressive behavior of form-filled sandwich panels with hybrid facesheet. The following conclusions can be drawn from the tests.

Under the impact energy of 30J, pure glass fiber laminates, hybrid laminates, and pure carbon fiber laminates are all penetrated. Fiber breaking and delamination came out as the main failure modes. The contact face of sandwich panels with pure carbon fabric cloth facesheet at impact energy of 30 J is completely penetrated, and the impact energy is absorbed by matrix cracking, fiber breaking and foam cracking. The impactor is rebounded during the impact event for panels with pure glass facesheet.

Factors that consume the impact energy are matrix cracking, debonding between fiber layers and foam core. Contact force, deformation and velocity decline ratio at peak force of this panel is respectively the lowest and largest among the three categories of materials.

A major focus of the current research was to critically assess the strength of the specimen after being impacted. Findings after conducting the experiment proved the compressive strength of sandwich panels was significantly reduced by impact load. Compressive strength decline ratio of the sandwich panels with pure carbon fiber facesheet has the maximum value of $76.37 \pm 11.18\%$ while panels with pure glass facesheet have the smallest decline ratio of $52.96 \pm 9.9\%$. Sandwich panels with hybrid facesheet could provide lower strength decline ratio of $65.22 \pm 5.58\%$ with relatively higher initial compressive strength.

Absorption of impact energy by panel with hybrid facesheet falls between specimen with pure glass and carbon fiber facesheet respectively. The main damage modes after impact found through visual inspection were propagated in forms such as cracking in the matrix, debonding between different layers and some fibers breaking in the hybrid facesheet. Impact properties of the hybrid panels is also largely influenced by the stacking effect of fibers. With carbon fiber as contact face better dynamic performance was observed since they could absorb more energy with higher maximum contact force.

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REFERENCES

- [1]. Evci, C. and M. Gülgeç, An experimental investigation on the impact response of composite materials. *International Journal of Impact Engineering*, 2012. **43**: p. 40-51.
- [2]. Christoforou, A.P., Impact dynamics and damage in composite structures. *Composite structures*, 2001. **52**(2): p. 181-188.
- [3]. Sutherland, L. and C.G. Soares, The effects of test parameters on the impact response of glass reinforced plastic using an experimental design approach. *Composites Science and Technology*, 2003. **63**(1): p. 1-18.
- [4]. Sutherland, L. and C.G. Soares, Impact characterisation of low fibre-volume glass reinforced polyester circular laminated plates. *International Journal of Impact Engineering*, 2005. **31**(1): p. 1-23.
- [5]. Hosur, M., M. Adbullah, and S. Jeelani, Studies on the low-velocity impact response of woven hybrid composites. *Composite Structures*, 2005. **67**(3): p. 253-262.
- [6]. Kim, J.-K. and K.-W. Kang, An analysis of impact force in plain-weave glass/epoxy composite plates subjected to transverse impact. *Composites Science and Technology*, 2001. **61**(1): p. 135-143.
- [7]. Tomblin, J.S., et al., Impact damage characterization and damage tolerance of composite sandwich airframe structures. 2001, *Wichita State Univ Ks*.
- [8]. Shyprykevich, P., et al., Guidelines for analysis, testing, and nondestructive inspection of impact-damaged composite sandwich structures. 2003, *Federal Aviation Administration Technical Center Atlantic City Nj*.
- [9]. Tomblin, J., et al., Damage tolerance of composite sandwich airframe structures-additional results. 2005, *FAA Technical Report DOT/FAA/AR-05/33, US Department of Transportation*
- [10]. Nettles, A. and J. Jackson, Developing a material strength design value based on compression after impact damage for the Ares I composite interstage. 2009.